

Review of Recent Research and Recommendations for Teaching the Alphabet in Early Childhood Settings

Author Details:

Jerry Aldridge, Ed.D., Jennifer L. Kilgo, Ed.D., Lynn D. Kirkland, Ed.D.
University of Alabama at Birmingham

Learning letter names and sounds is a tradition in most early childhood classrooms. Unfortunately, many strategies and activities used for teaching the alphabet in childcare, preschool, and kindergarten classrooms are not based on research. Some approaches teachers use are popular and pervasive and have become standard fare. Examples include singing the alphabet song (without looking at the letters) and using a “letter of the week” approach where teachers emphasize one letter per week to teach to the children. Such approaches are not based on research and waste valuable time that could be spent on more meaningful and evidence-based practices (Lusche, 2003; Meier, 2010).

What are authentic, evidence-based ways children can learn the alphabet? Many researchers have found two strategies to be meaningful and appropriate for learning the letters and sounds of the alphabet: (a) focusing on letters and sounds in children’s names (McKay & Teale, 2015; Pinnell & Fountas, 2011; Stahl, 2014); and (b) emphasizing words and letters in environmental print (Kirkland, Aldridge, & Kuby, 2007; Snow & Matthews, 2016). Evidence suggests that certain letters are much easier to learn than other letters. Letters found in children’s names are learned more quickly than less commonly used letters. In a study of preschoolers, “the initial letter of a child’s name was 11 times more likely to be known than a letter not in that child’s first name” (Stahl, 2014, p. 263). Furthermore, “teaching one letter a week doesn’t allow time to provide the level of intense practice for the letters that children need to learn the most difficult letters” (Stahl, 2014, p. 263). This is true of typically developing children, as well as children with delays or disabilities.

Researchers have found that one effective way to teach children the alphabet is to begin with letter names and then letter sounds because it just “makes sense to connect letter sound knowledge to students’ existing letter name knowledge” (Stahl, 2014, p. 262). Teaching the letters and sounds are attempted through three cycles that continue throughout the year. The three cycles are described in the following table.

Sequence for Teaching the Alphabet*

STRATEGY	REASON	EVIDENCE
<p>CYCLE ONE:</p> <p>Teach the initial letters of the children in the class</p>	<p>Many children already know the initial letter of their names in preschool and are interested in their friends’ names and “the amount of talk about letters during the morning message in Head Start classrooms predicted end-of-year alphabet knowledge” (Stahl, 2014, p. 264)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Stahl (2014)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Hindman & Wasik (2012)</p>
<p>CYCLE TWO:</p> <p>Continue to review the letters found in the children’s names and the <i>rest of the</i> letters, making sure each letter is explicitly taught, using alphabet books, songs, and games (as well as environmental print and Daily News that are also used in Circle Time)</p>	<p>“One set of skills consists of those that parents and preschool teachers value and actively promote: reciting the alphabet, recognizing and writing letters, writing one’s own name, reading environmental print...and knowing how to hold a book upright and turn pages” (Snow & Matthews, 2016, p. 58)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Snow & Matthews (2016)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Stahl (2014)</p>

<p>CYCLE THREE:</p> <p>review the letters in this order:</p> <p><i>(b, d, j, k, p, t, v, z)</i></p> <p><i>Then</i> <i>(f, l, m, n, r, s)</i></p> <p><i>Then MORE TIME to the following letters:</i> <i>(h, y, w, x, q and vowels)</i></p> <p><i>Then</i> <i>Letter name-letter sound relationships of the above letters</i></p> <p><i>Review letters that have similar features</i> <i>(b,d,p,q)</i></p> <p><i>Review letters in small groups beyond Circle Time (based on children’s progress) through shared writing, interactive writing, and independent writing.</i></p>	<p>Letter-name pronunciation advantage: CV sounds are taught first as needed, followed by VC sounds</p> <p>Ambiguous letters and vowels are taught later</p> <p>Some children need more time to discriminate between critical features of letters that are similar in form</p>	<p>Stahl (2014)</p> <p>Stahl (2014)</p> <p>Stahl (2014)</p> <p>Jones & Reutzel (2012)</p> <p>Hindman & Wasik (2012)</p> <p>Stahl (2014)</p>
<p>*Adapted from “New Insights About Letter Learning” by Katherine A. Dougherty Stahl (2014)</p>		

The three cycles rely on research-based strategies synthesized by Stahl (2014). In cycles two and three, children who are struggling may need more practice with letters and sounds and teachers are encouraged to continue to use children’s names to review, as well as environmental print, the morning news, and other words the children are learning.

Using Environmental Print

Environmental print is the print of everyday life and is defined as “print found in the natural environment of the child. This would include logos, labels, road signs, billboards, and other print found in the child’s immediate ecology” (Kirkland, Aldridge, & Kuby, 1991, p. 219). Environmental print is recognized for the fundamental and critical role it plays in the development of literacy and as one of the earliest steps in learning to read (Neumann, Hood, Ford, & Neuman, 2012). “Environmental print uses the prior knowledge of the students...[and] provides an authentic, legitimate purpose for learning” (Kirkland et al., 2007, p, xiii).

Consider the following example. A preschool teacher uses environmental print during circle time based on the following template adapted from Kirkland et al. (2007):

1. *Children are asked to bring to the classroom environmental print with which they are familiar and have experienced in some way.* The preschool teacher has an environmental print box for children to deposit the environmental print they bring to school. For example, four-year-old Rachel may bring in a napkin from Burger King, where she ate with her grandmother the night before, that has Burger King logo.
2. *At circle time, the teacher pulls one or more environmental print artifacts from the environmental print box.* One teacher, retrieving her student Rachel’s napkin from the box asks, “Who brought this?” Rachel

responds, “I went to Burger King with my grandmother last night.” Other children say, “I have a grandmother” and one child says, “I like your grandmother.”

3. *The teacher models writing the environmental print artifact, using standard manuscript, on a whiteboard or chart and then assists the child who brought the artifact in writing the word.* For example, the teacher writes the word Burger King and helps Rachel write the word for the other children to see. This step is important because researchers have found that young children often recognize environmental print logos but may not be aware that they can write the logo on a whiteboard, type the logo on a computer, or write the logo with a crayon on paper (Kuby & Aldridge, 1997; Kuby, Aldridge, & Snyder, 1994).
4. *The teacher asks the student and/or class to construct a sentence about the logo.* For example, the class may suggest, “Rachel had a good time at Burger King with her grandmother.” The teacher writes/models this sentence for children to see.
5. *Finally, the teacher asks the students to post the logo under the appropriate alphabet card on the wall.* Many preschool teachers have the alphabet cards displayed around the room as wall decoration and often above the blackboard. However, to access the letters when teaching with environmental print, the alphabet cards should be placed at eye level for the children to post environmental print on the appropriate alphabet card (Kirkland et al., 2007).
6. *After discussing environmental print, the teacher continues to highlight letters of the alphabet by focusing on the children’s names using the environmental print box.* For example, from Rachel’s experience at Burger King, the teacher asked, “Whose name begins with the letter ‘b’ like ‘burger’ in Burger King?” Or, “Who has the letter ‘b’ anywhere in their name?” Does anyone have the letter ‘k’ in their name like ‘King’ in Burger King?” The children’s names that begin with “b” or “k” are written down on a chart or smartboard for them to see, or the children are invited to come write their own names, pointing out the letter “b” or “k” in their name. Based on the goals and activities of the day, the teacher can also highlight other letters for the children to experience. For example, if the children are going to visit Porter’s Bakery in the afternoon, the teacher could say, “This afternoon we will visit Porter’s Bakery. Whose name begins with the letter ‘p’ in Porter?”

Utilizing Morning News Time

After focusing on letters and sounds of the alphabet based on children’s names and letters and words through environmental print, the early childhood class is now ready for the “Morning News,” which is sometimes referred to as morning meeting or circle time. Previously, this time was used to discuss the calendar and focus on the day, date, year, and weather report in which children learned to parrot the correct answers when prompted rather than understanding the concepts (Reich, 1994). The Morning News changed calendar activities to address concepts that met the levels of the children. The Morning News was designed to include the news of the day constructed by the children and the name of the day, a simple weather report, an environmental print report, and comments and questions about the day from the students (Goldman, Aldridge, & Worthington, 2003). Consider the example below.

The Morning News

Today is Thursday. It is sunny and cold outside. Rachel went to Burger King with her grandmother last night. We have grandmothers. We like Rachel’s grandmother. We will visit Carter’s Bakery today.

The need for early childhood teachers to utilize authentic, evidence-based strategies for young children to learn the alphabet has become increasingly apparent. Teachers are encouraged to implement strategies that are not only based on research, but are appropriate for and meaningful to young children (Kirkland et al., 2007). As described in this article, two promising strategies to teach letters and sounds of the alphabet to young children involve using the letters and sounds in the children’s names and emphasizing words and letters in environmental print during routine activities such as Morning News. Using strategies that are research-based,

appropriate, and meaningful to the children will benefit both typically developing children and those with delays or disabilities in attaining early literacy skills in an authentic manner.

References

- Goldman, R., Aldridge, J., & Worthington, L. (2003). *Teaching children to read*. Birmingham, AL: Seacoast.
- Hindman, A. H., & Wasik, B. (2012). Morning message time: An exploratory study in Head Start. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 40(5), 275-283.
- Jones, C. D., & Reutzel, D. R. (2012). Enhanced alphabet knowledge instruction: Exploring a change of frequency, focus and distributed cycles of review. *Reading Psychology*, 33(5), 448-464.
- Kirkland, L., Aldridge, J., & Kuby, P. (1999). Isn't that cute? Transforming the cute curriculum into authentic learning. *Focus of Pre-K & K*, 12(1), 1-3.
- Kirkland, L., Aldridge, J., & Kuby, P. (1991). Environmental print and the kindergarten classroom. *Reading Improvement*, 28, 219-222.
- Kirkland, L., Aldridge, J., & Kuby, P. (2007). *Integrating environmental print across the curriculum, preK-3: Making literacy instruction meaningful*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Kuby, P., & Aldridge, J. (1997). Direct versus indirect environmental print instruction and early reading ability in kindergarten children. *Reading Psychology: An International Quarterly*, 18, 91-104.
- Kuby, P., Aldridge, J., & Snyder, S. (1994). Developmental progression of environmental print recognition in kindergarten children. *Reading Psychology: An International Quarterly*, 15, 1-9.
- Lusche, P. (2003) *No more letter of the week: A framework for integrating reading strategies and cueing systems with letter-sound instruction*. Washington, DC: Staff Development for Educators.
- McKay, R., & Teale, W. H. (2015). *No more teaching a letter a week*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Meier, J. (2010). *N is for no letter of the week*. Retrieved from www.readingrockets.org/blog/39160
- Neumann, M. M., Hood, M., Ford, R.M., & Neumann, D. L. (2012). The role of environmental print in emergent literacy. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 12(3), 231-258.
- Pinnell, G. S., & Fountas, I. (2011). *Literacy beginnings: A prekindergarten handbook*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Reich, L. R. (1994). Circle time in preschool: An analysis of educational praxis. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 2(1), 51-59.
- Snow, C. E., & Matthews, T. J. (2016). Reading and language in the early grades. *The Future of Children*, 26(2), 57-74.
- Stahl, K. (2014). New insights about letter learning. *The Reading Teacher*, 68(4), 261-265.